

A LITERATURE REVIEW: IMPACT OF TECHNOSTRESS ON EMPLOYEE ENGAGEMENT IN THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION CONTEXT

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this paper is to summarise the literature related to the impact of technostress on employee engagement and the moderating effect of supervisor support and co-worker support on the relationship of technostress and employee engagement. This research uses a narrative review approach, including finding relevant research, summarising systematically research models, identifying hypotheses, assessing the limitations of previous research and giving recommendations for the following studies. A model with employee engagement as the dependent variable, technostress as the independent variable, and supervisor and co-worker support as moderators was identified in the previous research. The practical implication of this research demonstrates that technostress is one of the factors that affects on employee turnover intention. Additionally, this study offers some suggestions for further research into the effects of technostress on employee engagement in various organisational contexts.

Keywords: “Technostress”, “Employee engagement”, “Organisational engagement”, “Work engagement”, “Supervisor support”, “Co-worker support”, “Digital transformation”

Introduction

1. Rationale of the study

As early as 2020, the dynamic evolution of the Covid epidemic is changing customer transaction and payment behaviour, increasing demand for digital transformation of all companies. The use of new digital technologies such as social media, mobile technology, analytics, or embedded devices to enable major business improvements such as enhanced customer experiences, streamlined operations, or new business models is known as digital transformation (DT) (Fitzgerald et al., 2014). In a competitive context, it is critical for businesses to be more agile in a highly competitive market because there are numerous benefits to digital transformation such as

approaching customers, improving service quality, timely innovating products and quickly adapting to the market, improving security, creating a competitive advantage over competitors. In an educational context, new technology known as artificial intelligence (AI) has also introduced new opportunities, challenges, and possibilities for teachers and learners (Jafari, E., 2024).

However, the rapid growth in digital transformation is a “double-edged sword” that has resulted in a high level of stress among organisations’ employees as a result of technology development. The appearance of various uncertainties as a result of technological change in organisations caused stress on employees. This modern sickness of adaptation known as “technostress” is brought on by an inability to adapt to new computing technology in a positive manner (Brod, 1984). The literature on organisational employees and its effects on job outcomes have extensively researched technological stress, or the inability to adapt with changing technologies (Upadhyaya & Vrinda, 2021). Applying new technologies in organisational operations such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Electronic learning (E-learning) algorithms is expected to result in faster performance and a more productive mode. In addition, the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) in organisations makes officers spend more time working because of the remote working culture. The technostress may have appeared as a result of the high stress caused by digital transformation.

Those expectations cause office employees to be burned out, exhausted and less committed at work, which impacts their performance and wellbeing (Purisiol, 2019). The rapid change of technology leads to the pressure of digital transformation in several organisations, which is the cause of technostress in employees.

Moreover, this research will also review the role of social support in the context of digital transformation. Social support in the working context is divided by two typical sources: supervisor support and co-worker support. In the academic literature, these are commonly referred to as “perceived co-worker support” and “perceived supervisor support” (Guchait, Paşamehmetoğlu, & Dawson, 2014). The level to which employees believe their supervisors respect their contributions and attend to their general wellbeing is referred to as “perceived supervisor support” (PSS) (Guchait et al., 2014). On the other hand, “perceived co-worker support” (PCS) mentions to the degree that employees believe their co-workers will be willing to help them perform and complete work-related tasks. In other words, social support involves encouraging and supporting

co-workers as well as sharing knowledge and helping each another at work (Zhou & George, 2001). Therefore, employees who receive more support from their co-workers are more likely to have entry to more job-related resources that enable them to deal with stress, solve problems, enhance their work efficiency, and ultimately reduce stress and turnover (Guchait et al., 2014). Studies have identified social support as a mitigator that gives people the strength to handle challenging emotional workplace situations such as work stress and helps workers deal with the demands of their jobs (Chen & Feeley, 2014; Chiaburu & Harrison, 2008; Burke & Greenglass, 1993; Hobfoll et al., 1990).

2. Research objectives

The main purpose of this study is summarising the literature related to the impact of technostress influenced by digital transformation on employee engagement in organisations. This study also determines the previous research related to the moderating effect of social support, including supervisor support and co-worker support on the correlation between technostress and employee engagement.

Then, the results of this study will help future researchers have a comprehensive and systematic overview of previous studies to be able to further explore the impact of technological stress on employee engagement in the future.

Literature review and hypothesis identification

1. Technostress in digital transformation

Technostress

Stress is one of the major health threats, which has become a worldwide disease (Conner, 2014). According to Hart & Cooper (2002), the enlightened “psychological approach” to stress is also a relatively simplistic theory that views stress as occurring when job characteristics contribute to burnout, negative turnover, absenteeism, work dissatisfaction, and psychological distress. A variety of prominent stress models are extensively employed to portray stress’s implications and results to organisational behaviour. Firstly, in organisational stress research, the Person-Environment (P-E) Fit Model has been frequently employed. It is based on the widely held belief that organisations and their employees must find common ground in terms of how well the characteristics of individual employees (such as skill sets, abilities, personality, and competencies) and the organisation's environment (including culture, tasks, and job roles) match each other in mutually beneficial capacities. According to the P-E fit theory, workplace well-being is improved when there are little differences between

person and environmental factors. However, the P-E model appears to ignore individual variability and subjective well-being aspects that may vary personal or situational experiences, resulting in mismatch. Secondly, The Job Demand-Control (JDC) model, developed by Karasek (1979) and regarded as one of the most prominent conceptual frameworks, provides better empirical insights into structural aspects of the workplace that expose employees to stressful encounters. The approach focuses on the amount to which job control is allowed to mitigate the impact of work demands. It posits that poor health occurs when employees are subjected to high levels of work demands while having disproportionate levels of autonomy or job control. Thirdly, a theoretical foundation of stress from the research of Demerouti et al. (2001) based on Demand-Resource model (JD-R model) divided type of work conditions into job applications and job resources. This model accepts that the risk of exhaustion is greatest in work environments with high job demand and limited job resources (Demerouti et al., 2001).

Stress is also defined as a psychological reaction to a type of imbalance between a person and its surroundings (Ragu-Nathan et al., 2008). In the context of digital technology development, the use of new information and communication technologies (NICT) at work is a topic that beginning to receive special attention. There are some researchers who have studied on NICT as one of the workplace stressors. The ability to access information through the use of wireless devices that are not limited by location or time can transform work structures into more flexible working environments where job demand is high and job resources are limited (Cousins & Robey, 2015; Diaz et al., 2012). Working remotely allows employees to choose a convenient working location, but it also requires employees to participate in their work for longer than the official working hours. Moreover, stress comes in two flavours: eustress and distress. Eustress, also defined as normal or advantageous stress, is when a person feels as a challenge to overcome, and that stress leads to a positive outcome. Yet, distress, also referred to as unpleasant stress, is a state of exhaustion brought on by a person's perception that an information system poses a threat and has an unfavourable impact (Upadhyaya & Vrinda, 2021).

Technostress is the modern worldwide disease that is a result of negative adaptation to new computing technology (Brod, 1984). This kind of stress on employees may have appeared because of the high stress caused by digital transformation in organisations. Technological stressors of technostress include emails, messaging apps,

computers, mobile phones, other software systems, hardware systems, new technological systems, etc. Moreover, the Covid-19 pandemic has accelerated the digital transformation process of organisations to meet the customer needs and boost corporate rivalry, but it has also sped up the accessing technology process which could lead to technostress. A previous study showed that employees who work remotely engage in more hours with high workload, which increases the amount of techno-stressors like technological invasion in their lives (Savolainen et al., 2021). In addition, another study confirmed that techno-overload, techno-insecurity, techno-invasion, techno-uncertainty, and techno-complexity are five “technostress creators” that contribute to technostress (Tarafdar et al., 2007). On the other hand, technostress inhibitors included technical support, literacy facilitation and engagement facilitation, are organisational mechanisms that reduce the consequences of technological stress on workers (Ragu-Nathan et al., 2008). Moreover, other types of technostress inhibitors include perceived supervisor support (PSS), technology efficacy and adjusting regulatory focus (Wang, X., Tan, & Li, 2020). In the context of workplace, there are several negative consequences associated with technostress, such as distractions, job dissatisfaction, insufficient job involvement, poor work performance, job demand ambiguity, lowered well-being, absenteeism, rising strain, exhaustion, and burnout, lowered innovation ability, and unwilling compliance or noncompliance with technology requirements imposed by the organisation (Spiros, 2019). Table 1.1 below shows the summary of previous research on technostress.

Table 1.1. Literature review of previous researches on technostress

Research	Antecedents	Techno-stressors	Additional variables	Independent variables
<u>Tarafdar et al. (2007)</u>	N/A	Techno-uncertainty, techno-invasion, techno-overload, techno-insecurity and techno-complexity	N/A	Role overload, productivity, role conflict and role stress
<u>Ragu-Nathan et al. (2008)</u>	Age, gender, education, computer confidence	Techno-uncertainty, techno-invasion, techno-overload, techno-insecurity and techno-complexity	Technostress inhibitors (literacy facilitation, technical support provision and involvement facilitation)	Job satisfaction, organisational commitment, continuance commitment
<u>Wang, K., Shu,</u>	Personal	Techno-overload,	N/A	N/A

<u>and Tu (2008)</u>	characteristics (gender, age and educational levels); and organisational characteristics (centralisation and innovation)	techno-invasion, techno-complexity, techno-insecurity, and techno-uncertainty		
<u>Jena (2015)</u>	N/A	Techno-overload, techno-invasion, techno-complexity, techno-insecurity, and techno-uncertainty	N/A	Job satisfaction
<u>Okolo, Kamarudin, and Ahmad (2018)</u>	Job design (skill variety, task identity, task significance, task feedback and job autonomy)	Techno-overload, techno-complexity and techno-invasion	Technostress	Employee engagement
<u>Mohammed (2022)</u>	N/A	Techno-overload, techno-invasion, techno-complexity, techno-insecurity, and techno-uncertainty	Perceived supervisor support	Work engagement
<u>Andrulli and Gerards (2023)</u>	Job design	Techno-overload, techno-invasion, techno-complexity, techno-insecurity, and techno-uncertainty	Meaningful work	Work-Related Well-Being

Digital transformation and technostress

The recent surge in digital technology adoption has pushed this issue to the forefront of discussions. There are numerous definitions for the term “digital transformation (DT)” and two terms “digitalization” and “digital age” are frequently used synonymously (Susanne et al., 2015). In a literature review, Stolterman et al. (2004) argued that digital transformation refers to the changes that digital technology causes or influences for all parts of a person's life. The other author agreed with Stolterman’s definition that the changes that digital technology causes or influences in

all aspects of human life are referred to as digital transformation (Kokkinakos et al., 2016). The use of technology to significantly increase an enterprise's performance or reach is known as “digital transformation” and it is quickly gaining popularity among businesses all around the world. In addition to utilising digital innovations like analytics, mobile, social media, and smart embedded devices, executives across all industries are also enhancing their usage of more established technologies that can alter customer interactions, internal procedures, and value propositions (Westerman et al., 2011). The other article also mentioned the same definition that the term “digital transformation” refers to the changing (or “adaptation”) of business strategies as a result of the rapid speed of technological advancement and innovation that results in shifts in customer and societal behaviour (Kotarba, 2018). Everyone is affected by digital transformation, and the power of digital technology can be applied to every aspect of an organisation (Kozarkiewicz, 2020). Digital transformation refers to the use of new digital technologies such as social media, mobile technology, analytics, or embedded devices to enable major business improvements such as improved customer experiences, streamlined operations, or new business models (Fitzgerald et al., 2014). Organisations are making a concerted effort to adapt to new ways, most of which are related to the world's digital transformation, which are artificial intelligence (AI), electronic learning (E-learning) and the internet of things (IoT).

Besides the opportunities of digital transformation that the organisations receive, one of the biggest challenges of digital transformation that organisations face is the stress to advance online before the others. The workforce’s technological knowledge is crucial for the success of digital transformation; however, when designing digital transformation, organisations must consider the cultural shifts they will experience as staff members and organisational leaders learn to use and rely on novel technologies (Ebert & Duarte, 2016). On the other hand, employees have typically worked according to their routines and traditional methods for a long time and do not like to be managed by technology. The lack of knowledge to handle several new technologies at the same time causes stress for employees. Moreover, as a result of the digital transformation, many businesses have had to alter the business model, eliminating many manual jobs and replacing them with automated ones. This has put pressure on employees because of reducing workforces.

In recent times, “the Fourth Industrial Revolution” has served as an imperative for the implementation of technology in business. “The Industrial Revolution 4.0” is changing the way businesses operate, how they do business, and how consumers behave, due to the rapid development of high-speed internet, blockchain technology and cloud computing (Tan et al., 2021). Moreover, the global outbreak of COVID-19 made 2020 a challenging year for the economics, education and other industries around the world. However, this pandemic also plays an important role in accelerating digital transformation across all industries because the “work from home” movement forces us to adapt to new manners of working and demands for new digital services (Do et al., 2022).

2. Technostress and employee engagement

Employee engagement

Employee engagement is a widespread concept in the organisations and behaviour academic fields (Robinson et al., 2004). The word “engagement” denotes dedication, passion, involvement, zeal, effort, and energy, and other things. According to Saks (2006), employee engagement is the degree to which an individual is engaged and absorbed in their work environment, rather than an attitude. In addition, Kahn defines engagement as a psychological presence at work (Kahn (1990, 1992)). Significantly, Kahn’s conceptualization of engagement can be applied in two contexts: the employee's work role and the employee's role as an individual member of an organisation. According to Saks’ (2006) research, organisational and work engagement are distinct categories with independent causes and implications. Therefore, employee engagement can be divided by two dimensions: work engagement (or job engagement) and organisational engagement.

On the one hand, work engagement is defined as “emotional involvement or commitment” and the state of being in “gear” by Merriam Webster's dictionary. The first definition of work engagement was mentioned and developed in the research of Kahn (1990). The definition of work engagement is “the harnessing of organisation members' selves to their work role; in engagement, people employ and express themselves physically, cognitively, and emotionally during role performance.” In other words, work engagement motivated people to work more because they identify with their employment. While personal disengagement is defined as “the uncoupling of selves from work roles; in disengagement, people withdraw and defend themselves physically,

cognitively, or emotionally during role performances” (Kahn, 1990, p. 694). In addition, work engagement was explained as an intellectual and emotional dedication to an organisation (Richman, 2006). Furthermore, engagement is defined as psychological appearance as well but adds that it also includes two major elements: attention and absorption. Attention is defined as “cognitive availability and the amount of time spent thinking about a role,” whereas absorption is defined as “being engrossed in a role and refers to the intensity of one's focus on a role” (Rothbard, 2001, p. 656).

On the other hand, organisational engagement refers to a person's attitude and attachment to their organisation. Engagement is not a behaviour; it is the extent to which an individual is attentive and absorbed in their roles in an organisation. Organisational engagement refers to the level that employees classify with the people, values, mission, and culture of their organisation (Bahr et al., 2014). Bahr (2014) asserted that organisational engagement is about how emotionally connected people are to their organisation, how passionate and enthusiastic they are, and how motivated they are to support the goals of the business. Moreover, while organisational commitment action includes voluntary and informal behaviours that can benefit coworkers and the organisation, the priority of engagement is on one's formal role performance rather than extended role and voluntary attitudes. Moreover, job involvement differs from engagement because job involvement, according to May et al. (2004), is the outcome of a cognitive judgement about job satisfaction and is related to one's personality.

In summary, employee engagement is distinguished by several related concepts, the most notable of which are organisational engagement and job engagement.

Impact of technostress on employee engagement

Employee engagement described initially as “the harnessing of organisational members selves to their work roles” by Kahn (1990, p. 694). Tims et al. (2013) added that a person who is actively and successfully immersed in their work is mentally, emotionally, and sincerely committed to it. Employee engagement in this study is based on Saks (2006) elements of employee engagement. Saks (2006) separated employee engagement into two categories: work engagement and organisational engagement. Kahn (1990) explained that having the necessary mental, physical, and psychological resources is a prerequisite for being committed at work. Moreover, Okolo et al. (2018) argued that employee engagement and technostress are theoretically related. In the past, technological stress may exhaust those mental and emotional resources, which could

lead to disengagement on the part of the workforce. According to Velnampy et al. (2013), an excessive amount of technological stress lowers employee engagement, which is a common conclusion drawn from the stress literature. A finding revealed that technostress creators have a negative effect on job satisfaction (Kot, 2022). In addition, a study (Ragu-Nathan et al., 2008) revealed that technological stressors lower job satisfaction, which in turn lowers organisational and continuation commitment. Moreover, information and communications technologies (ICT) use that increases already high levels of job stress can have detrimental impacts on people's cognitive, psychological, and physical health as well as on organisations (e.g., decreased employee commitment and satisfaction) (Atanasoff et al., 2017). Working under situations where ICT technology and devices are present throughout the time is a requirement in an increasing range of professions and jobs (Biela, 2018). This worsened during the time of increased remote work intensity brought on by the pandemic (Wang et al., 2020). The existence of factors that cause technostress, including techno-overload, techno-invasion, techno-complexity, techno-insecurity, and techno-uncertainty is linked to lower job satisfaction. Similar to the conclusion of Kot (2022), Aktan & Toraman (2022) argue that working under technologically stressful conditions may result in a drop in job satisfaction, which can have a number of detrimental effects on both the employees themselves (dissatisfaction, decreased employee engagement, professional burnout). However, in some newest studies, there are some contradictory conclusions. Mohammed (2022) concluded that there is no connection or weak positive relationship between technostress and work engagement while this conclusion is similar to studies of Okolo et al. (2018) and Schmidt (2018). The previous research suggested that stress does not always lower employee engagement but that a moderate amount of stress can be motivating while a lot of stress can have a negative effect on people.

Because of the opposing viewpoints, to identify the relationship between technostress and employee engagement in the context of digital transformation in a developing country, this study identifies the first hypothesis as follow:

H₁: Technostress influenced by digital transformation has a negative effect on employee engagement.

3. Social support and its impact on the relationship between technostress and employee engagement

Social support

Social support is referred to as a flow of psychological concern and instrumental support between people (Weiss, 1983, p.31). Someone who receives social support feels or perceives that they are cared for by others that they are revered and appreciated by others and that they are part of a network of people who exchange assistance and obligations (Wills and Cohen, 1985). Social support can come from a variety of people, including partners, relatives, friends or co-workers (Allen et al., 2002).

In the workplace, supervisor support and co-worker support are the two main dimensions of social support. These are frequently referred to as “perceived supervisor support” and “perceived co-worker support” (Guchait et al., 2014). “Perceived supervisor support” is the extent to which workers perceive their managers appreciate their contributions and care about their general well-being while “perceived co-worker support” refers to the extent to which employees think their co-workers will be willing to assist them in carrying out and finishing work-related tasks (Guchait et al., 2014). Supervisor support can be identified as a fundamental factor to a supportive work environment during the employee development process. Workers' perceived supervisor support in employee development activities has been demonstrated to empirically affect employees' intentions to engage and the true participation ratio in employee development activities (Brands, 2016). Thus, social support entails motivating and assisting co-workers as well as knowledge sharing and offering guidance at the workplace (Zhou & George, 2001). Accordingly, workers who experience more co-worker support are more likely to have access to more job-related resources that will help them manage stress, find solutions to problems, improve their work efficiency and ultimately lower stress and turnover (Guchait et al., 2014).

Moreover, Cobb (1976) defines social support as behaviours that occur during social transactions of communications that make their recipients feel cared for, esteemed and loved. Social support is given and received by social contacts with varied degrees of connection. It can be used to give advice, help with issues, express personal concerns, and, when appropriate, comfort and encouragement (Agneessens et al., 2006). According to Mack and Rhineberger-Dunn (2019), social support is the result of interpersonal work interactions that has the capacity to improve the recipient's well-

being or coping capacities. It has also been defined as others' helpful activities (Deelstra et al., 2003). Therefore, social support refers to organisational connections from supervisors, colleagues, and subordinates. However, in this study, subordinator support has been eliminated.

Moderating effect of social support on the relationship between technostress and employee engagement

According to Conservation of Resource (COR) Theory (Hobfoll, 1989), a stress theory that explains the drive that motivates humans to preserve current resources while also seeking new ones. When it comes to handling job demands and, in this study, digital transformation demands, resources such as social support can be invaluable. In fact, social support could be used to help employees manage technology more effectively, minimising the effects of technostress (Hobfoll and Freedy, 1993). Under COR Theory, individuals who receive more support are better able to maintain their psychological and physical wellness in stressful situations and, in general, throughout their lives. Similar findings were reported in research by Ducharme et al. (2007): work-based social support, particularly supervisor support and colleague support, effectively reduced participants' feelings of emotional tiredness and stress, and hence lowered their intentions to leave.

Moreover, employees' secession or resignation from the workplace is also influenced by co-worker relationships (Dorothea, 2015). Secession or resignation can arise because of social or structural factors. Lack of support and interactions might result in unmet interpersonal connection demands. Employees will appreciate and feel positive relationships with managers and co-workers when supervisor and co-worker support are high, and they will feel engaged in the organisation. Individuals will aim to achieve the functional purpose of interpersonal interactions and psychological needs, according to the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) (Deci and Ryan, 1985). When co-worker relationships are positive, employees feel capable of meeting their demands and are driven to expand their dedication to the organisation. Social support from supervisors and co-workers could include the providing of information and resources, support, empathy, guidance, and a variety of other forms that assist employees in their work (Chiaburu & Harrison, 2008). Relationships and encouragement from managers and peers will drive employees to execute things that are not part of their job description and to feel at ease in the organisation. Previous study has shown that the role of social

support from supervisors and co-workers as a force that supports the work has an impact on employee engagement (May et al., 2004; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2004). Previous study indicates that social support has an impact on employee engagement at the workplace.

On the one hand, co-worker relationships are a significant source of support for employees and have a favourable effect on employee satisfaction (Madlock and Booth-Butterfield, 2012). In general, employees having a strong relationship with their colleagues will be beneficial to have healthy mental and physical health. While employee interactions with supervisors are dependent on their position in the authority hierarchy, co-worker relationships are flat and lack any formal authority features (Basford and Offermann, 2012). Therefore, co-workers cannot be ruled, yet the colleague relationships are an important part of their daily working lives and the results of such a relationship include physically sharing in the office and being part of a work team. Co-workers play an essential role in the organisation by developing informal networks that emerge spontaneously and unplanned. According to a previous study, employees prefer to express ideas and difficulties connected to their work to co-workers rather than to a more formal party such as a supervisor. Trust in co-workers can generate a lot of social sources (Prusak and Cohen, 2001).

On the other hand, there are various effective techniques to alleviate stress, including social support and physical activity. In general, having a support system is really beneficial when dealing with stress. Specifically, supervisor support is adversely associated with stress (Morgan et al., 2019). Technostress can contribute to work fatigue, hence diminishing job satisfaction, but supportive leadership can minimise work exhaustion and raise job satisfaction (Fieseler, Grubenmann, Meckel and Müller, 2014). Furthermore, Human Resource Management effectiveness (HRMe) moderates the negative association between technology-related overload and perceived organisational support, making the effect less powerful when HRMe is high (Harris, Lambert & Harris, 2013). Thus, supervisor support and co-worker support may be important factors of workplace stress.

Specifically, in a previous study, Cohen and Wills (1985) attempted to develop a buffering model for social support and discovered data that characterised social support as a resource required to assist the individual in stressful circumstances. According to research by Fisher, Sanchez, and Viswesvaran (1999), social support has been shown to have three main impacts: (1) it lessens strain (reaction to stressors), (2) it lessens the

strength of the stressor, and (3) it lessens the effects of stressors on strain. Additionally, Viswesvaran and associates (1999) demonstrate that social support moderates stress rather than suppresses it. The majority of workplace research investigated social support from the standpoint of the sources of support (like supervisor and co-worker support). Studies by Frese and Gielnik (2014) support and illustrate social support as a moderator on various relationships between various constructs, such as stress and psychological well-being. Additionally, the stress buffering model has highlighted social support as a reliever or mitigator, explaining how it lessens the negative effects of job stress and enhances an individual's wellbeing (Dean et al., 1990). Additionally, it has been suggested that perceived social support from an organisation, a supervisor, and coworkers may act as important moderators to lessen the detrimental effects of emotional work on employee well-being (Eisenberger et al., 2001). Specifically, because of the above literature review, this research has posed the topic of whether social support helps to reduce the relationship between technostress and employee's job intention in the context of digital transformation.

Therefore, this study identifies the second and the third hypotheses as below:

H₂: Supervisor support reduces negative impacts of technostress influenced by digital transformation on employee engagement.

H₃: Co-worker support reduces negative impacts of technostress influenced by digital transformation on employee engagement.

Limitation of previous studies and recommendation for further studies

Technostress is not a new topic in the world, but in a developing country, there are few studies on this subject that need to be expanded. Therefore, investigating the impact of technostress on employee engagement is one of the topics that need to be researched.

There is a lack of research and literature in developing countries context-setting regarding the moderating effects of social support. Most studies have been done and focused on direct relationships between stress and employee engagement. Additionally, research that looked into the moderating role of various forms of social support in the relationship between stress and employee engagement was not investigated, particularly in developing countries. Therefore, it is essential to research how social support moderates the connection between technological stress and employee engagement in the digital transformation process in developing countries.

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